

ISic2975

I.Sicily inscription 2975

Language

Latin

Type

honorific (?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

(eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.59 ph

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